

Kinetics of Oxidation of Acetophenone Oximes by Chromium(VI)

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Kinetics of the oxidation of acetophenone oxime and its *para*-substituted derivatives by chromium (VI) has been studied at 30°. The product analysis indicates that the reaction is oxidative hydrolysis. The rate increases with the increase in concentration of hydrogen ions. The first order rate dependence on the substrate concentration and inverse dependence on chromium(VI) concentration are observed. The effect of DMF on the rate suggests that the reaction is of ion-dipole type. The activation parameters are activation energy (ΔE^\ddagger) 14.4 kcal mol⁻¹ and entropy (ΔS^\ddagger) -30.5 cal K⁻¹ mol⁻¹. The studies on substituent effect gave a negative reaction constant ($\rho = -0.7$) which suggests that the electron donating substituent favours the reaction. A mechanism involving the formation of an iminoxy radical in the rate determining step is proposed.

OXIDATIVE hydrolysis¹ of oximes is generally utilised for the preparation of ketones since acid hydrolysis of oximes to ketones does not proceed in high yield. Not much work is done on the kinetics² of oxidative hydrolysis of the substituted acetophenone oximes with chromium(VI).

It has been observed by the present authors that chromium(VI) in mineral acid solution (HClO₄ or HCl) converts acetophenone oxime (APO) or its *para*-substituted compounds into the respective ketones at a measurable rate. Hence the kinetic study is carried out in these acid media.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of AnalaR or G.R. (Merck) grade. Acetophenone oxime or its *para*-substituted derivative were prepared from the corresponding ketones by the standard procedure³. The oximes were dissolved in *N,N'*-dimethylformamide (E. Merck) and the resulting solutions were used in the studies. The reaction was monitored spectrophotometrically under pseudo-first order conditions in presence of excess oxime. The decrease in the absorbance due to disappearance of Cr^{VI} was followed at different time intervals at 450 nm. A correction for Cr^{III} absorbance was made by subtracting the absorbance read out at 640 nm from the absorbance at 450 nm. Blank experiments revealed that under the experimental conditions the absorbance of Cr^{III} at 450 nm was the same as that at 640 nm and Cr^{VI} did not show any absorbance at this wavelength. It was also confirmed that Cr^{VI} obeyed Beer's law at 450 nm in the concentration range studied.

Results and Discussion

Effect of oxidant: The disappearance of Cr^{VI} follows first order rate law and the rate constant decreased with the increase in initial concentration of Cr^{VI} (Table 1). Such behaviour is, however, not uncommon with Cr^{VI} oxidations⁴ and shows that acid chromate ion (HCrO₄⁻) is the effective oxidant⁵. Increasing dilution increases the proportionate concentration of HCrO₄⁻ ion⁶. Each experiment was performed at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 1.2 M$) maintained by the addition of sodium perchlorate.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF OXIDANT ON REACTION RATE
[APO] = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, [H⁺] = 0.05 M, $\mu = 1.2 M$, Temp. = 30°

[Cr ^{VI}] $\times 10^3 M$	<i>k</i> $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$
3.0	1.4
2.5	1.6
2.0	2.3
1.5	3.6

Effect of substrate: The data in Table 2 show that the rate of oxidation increased with the increase in concentration of oxime and showed first order dependence on the oxime concentration. Plot of $1/k$ vs $1/[\text{oxime}]$ gave a straight line passing through the origin suggesting that there is no prior complex formation between the oxidant and the substrate. However, this does not always rule out the possibility of formation of transitory oxidant-substrate complex. It rather indicates that the formation constant of such an intermediate complex is very low.

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TABLE 2—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANT WITH SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATION

[Oxime] $\times 10^3 M$	k $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$	$k/[Oxime]$ $\times 10^4$
1.0	2.31	2.31
1.5	3.53	2.35
2.0	4.80	2.40
2.5	5.90	2.36
3.0	7.68	2.56

Effect of acid concentration: The acid dependence of the reaction rate was studied at fixed substrate and oxidant concentrations in the range 0.05–1.2 M HCl and 0.025–0.6 M HClO₄. Sodium chloride and sodium perchlorate were used to keep the ionic strength constant at 1.2 M in HCl and HClO₄ media. From the data in Table 3, it is seen that the rate is higher in HClO₄ than in HCl. It is further observed that the reaction showed a fractional order dependence on hydrogen ion concentration.

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF RATE CONSTANT ON ACID CONCENTRATION

Acid concn. M	In presence of HCl k $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$	In presence of HClO ₄ k $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$
0.025	—	1.3
0.050	1.8	2.3
0.100	2.3	3.7
0.200	2.5	4.9
0.400	2.8	6.7
0.600	3.1	8.3
0.800	3.4	—
1.000	3.6	—
1.200	4.0	—

Effect of salt concentration: Addition of sodium chloride in presence of 0.2 M HCl decreased the rate whereas the addition of sodium perchlorate in presence of 0.2 M HClO₄ increased the rate slightly (Table 4). This shows that chloride ion exhibit a retarding influence on the reaction. The retarding influence of chloride ion may be attributed to the formation of a less active oxidant species

species with acid chromate ion. However, ionic strength showed a little positive effect on the rate with NaClO₄. This indicates that the reaction is possibly of an ion–dipole type.

Effect of temperature: Rate increased with temperature and plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ is linear (Table 5). Activation energy (ΔE^*) and activation entropy (ΔS^*) evaluated from the linear plot are 14.4 kcal mol⁻¹ and -30.5 cal K⁻¹ mol⁻¹, respectively. The activation entropy value points out that the reaction is bimolecular⁸.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF ANIONS ON RATE CONSTANT

HCl		HClO ₄	
NaCl M	k $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$	NaClO ₄ M	Rate constant k $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$
0.0	4.5	0.0	4.5
0.2	4.2	0.2	4.5
0.4	3.7	0.4	4.8
0.6	3.0	0.6	4.9
0.8	2.8	0.8	4.9
1.0	2.5	1.0	4.9

TABLE 5—TEMPERATURE EFFECT ON RATE CONSTANT

Temp °C	k $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$
30	2.3
35	3.4
40	5.1

Effect of solvent: The studies carried out in aquo-DMF solutions showed that the rate is higher in solutions containing higher percentage of water, i.e. having higher dielectric constant (Table 6). It is obvious that the rate increases with the increase in dielectric constant. The reaction⁹ is therefore between (i) two molecules forming a polar product, and (ii) two ions of same sign/opposite sign and neutral molecule.

 TABLE 6—DEPENDENCE OF RATE CONSTANT ON DMF–H₂O COMPOSITION

[APO]= 1×10^{-3} M, [CrVI]= 2×10^{-3} M, [H⁺]=0.05 M, $\mu=1.2$ M, Temp.=30°

DMF %(v/v)	k $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$
10	8.8
20	6.1
30	3.9
40	2.3
50	1.3
60	0.7

Effect of substituent: It is observed that the rate increased as the electron-donating nature of the substituent increased (Table 7). A linear plot with a negative slope ($\rho=-0.7$) is obtained when $\log k$ is plotted against ρ . This suggests that a hydrogen atom¹⁰ is lost in the initial reaction since it is established¹¹ that the first step is a one-electron step involving the formation of an iminoxyl radical in the oxidation of oximes.

Effect of Mn^{II} ions: Watanabe and Westheimer¹² successfully used the induced oxidation of Mn^{II} as a diagnostic tool to determine oxidation state of the intermediate chromium species Cr^V or Cr^{IV}. However, in the present investigations, the rate did not change even in presence of 1×10^{-3} M of Mn^{II}.

TABLE 7—EFFECT OF SUBSTITUENT ON RATE OF HYDROLYSIS AT 30°

$[X-C_6H_4-C=NOH]=1 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Cr^{VI}]=2 \times 10^{-3} M$,
 $[H^+]=0.05 M$, $\mu=1.2 M$

Substituent X	ρ	k $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$
p-NO ₂	0.78	0.59
p-Cl	0.23	1.80
H	0.00	2.30
p-Me	-0.17	2.82
p-OMe	-0.27	3.21

By separate polarographic experiments it is shown that acid hydrolysis of the oxime under the experimental conditions is negligible and that the products of the reaction in presence of Cr^{VI} are the ketone, and oxidation products of hydroxylamine. From these observations, the following mechanism is proposed.

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